

The Share-VDE ontology: a BIBFRAME extension for linked data discovery^{*}

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Abstract. This paper describes the Share-VDE ontology, an extension to BIBFRAME. While the ontology supports the discovery functionality of Share-VDE and the Share family search systems, it may be re-used in any system requiring a bridge among BIBFRAME, IFLA LRM and RDA. Classes discussed in this paper include the `svde:Opus`, `svde:OpusType`, and `svde:Work`. The Share-VDE ontology achieves interoperability among the major bibliographic models by asserting that bibliographic entities are described by attribute sets. The attribute set modeling approach is a departure from the conceptual modeling that has informed the development of nearly all modern linked data models.

Keywords: BIBFRAME · Interoperability · Linked Data Discovery · RDA · IFLA LRM · Ontology Development.

1 Introduction

The Share-VDE discovery environment is a linked data search system that applies the BIBFRAME vocabulary [1]. Overall goals for describing the Share-VDE ontology using the web ontology language [2] include using semantic web principles to publish the classes, properties and constraints that are used in the Share Family of initiatives (<https://share-family.org>); to clarify the relationship among Share-VDE entities and other linked data vocabularies; and to provide internal and external consistency to classes and properties used in the Share-VDE discovery system. The major overarching design principle is to re-use existing linked data vocabularies to reduce redundancy and ambiguity. The Share-VDE ontology was developed as an extension to the BIBFRAME vocabulary [3] and supports the features of the Share-VDE discovery environment [4]. The Protégé ontology editor has functionality for imports from external ontology files on the web [5]. To provide clarity to the relationship among Share-VDE classes and existing bibliographic linked data vocabularies, RDA Work and Expression classes [6], RDA unconstrained elements, and the IFLA LRM conceptual model [7] were

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added as imports to the base BIBFRAME vocabulary import in the Share-VDE ontology:

```
<rdf:RDF xmlns="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#" xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#" xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#" xmlns:skos="http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#" xmlns:terms="http://purl.org/dc/terms/">
<Ontology rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology">
<imports rdf:resource="http://www.rdaregistry.info/xml/Elements/c.xml"/>
<imports rdf:resource="http://www.rdaregistry.info/xml/Elements/e.xml"/>
<imports rdf:resource="http://www.rdaregistry.info/xml/Elements/u.xml"/>
<imports rdf:resource="http://www.rdaregistry.info/xml/Elements/w.xml"/>
<imports rdf:resource="http://iflaststandards.info/ns/lrm/lrmer.xml"/>
<imports rdf:resource="https://id.loc.gov/ontologies/bibframe.rdf"/>
```

Remark 1. The namespaces and imports apply to all RDF/XML in the paper.

2 Methods

The ontology editing process began by examining the existing Share-VDE classes that were previously described as a conceptual model; documenting existing classes using RDF/XML markup in OWL; moving next to the object properties; the working group concluded by adding constraints such as disjoint statements to classes. The core Share-VDE classes are the Opus, the OpusType, and the Work. The conceptual diagram informing the development of the ontology is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Core classes described in the SVDE Ontology.

3 Results

This sections describes an annotation property, the object properties, and the classes used in the Share-VDE ontology. The ontology will include named individuals of the OpusType class, these are not yet ready for publication.

Share-VDE Annotation Property : closeMatch

```
<AnnotationProperty rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/closeMatch">
  <rdfs:label>close match to</rdfs:label>
  <skos:definition>Refers to a semantically similar entity (
    typically class or property) in another ontology or scheme.</
    skos:definition>
  <skos:scopeNote>The svde:closeMatch is different than the skos:
    closeMatch in the sense that the annotation property is
    designed for annotation of classes whereas the skos:closeMatch
    provides a mechanism for relating class individuals. The svde
    :closeMatch annotation does not directly connect any of the
    classes that are the focus of annotation.</skos:scopeNote>
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://purl.org/dc/terms/
    relation"/>
</AnnotationProperty>
```

Share-VDE Object Properties : hasExpression, hasType, hasOpusType, and inHub.

```
<ObjectProperty rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/hasExpression">
  <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/Opus"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/Work"/>
  <rdfs:label>hasExpression</rdfs:label>
  <svde:closeMatch rdf:resource="http://iflaststandards.info/ns/lrm/
    lrm/r/R2"/>
  <svde:closeMatch rdf:resource="http://rdaregistry.info/Elements/w/
    P10078"/>
</ObjectProperty>
```

Remark 2. The svde:hasExpression provides a relation among the svde:Opus and svde:Work.

```
<ObjectProperty rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/hasType">
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://rdaregistry.info/Elements
    /u/P60944"/>
  <rdfs:label>hasType</rdfs:label>
  <skos:definition>The svde:hasType is an intermediate property that
    may be specialized by entity.</skos:definition>
</ObjectProperty>
```

Remark 3. The `svde:hasType` is utilized to specify object property categorization.

```
<ObjectProperty rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/hasOpusType">
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/
    hasType"/>
  <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/Opus"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/OpusType"/>
  <rdfs:label>hasOpusType</rdfs:label>
</ObjectProperty>
```

Remark 4. The `svde:OpusType` individuals are related to the `svde:Opus` using the object property `svde:hasOpusType`.

```
<ObjectProperty rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/inHub">
  <rdfs:subPropertyOf rdf:resource="http://rdaregistry.info/Elements
    /u/P61042"/>
  <svde:usageNote>A bf:Hub may be related to one or many svde:Works.
  </svde:usageNote>
  <svde:useDomain rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/Work"/>
  <svde:useRange rdf:resource="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/bibframe
    /Hub"/>
</ObjectProperty>
```

Remark 5. A discovery feature of the Share-VDE system will utilize the `bf:Hub` in grouping translations of the same `Work`. Other use cases for applying the `bf:Hub` are being planned. These include grouping different versions or adaptations of the same `svde:Work`.

Share-VDE Classes : Opus, OpusType, and Work

```
<Class rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/Opus">
  <disjointWith rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/Work"/>
  <terms:relation rdf:resource="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/
    bibframe/Hub"/>
  <rdfs:label>Opus</rdfs:label>
  <skos:definition>The svde:Opus is a distinct conceptual outcome of
    artistic or intellectual activity. The highest level of
    abstraction in Share-VDE, an Opus is an entity that permits
    the grouping of works that are considered functional or near
    equivalents. The Opus is defined by a constellation of
    elements that form the shared content of works and provides a
    grouping for svde:Work entities.</skos:definition>
  <skos:note>The Opus is not the same as the bf:Hub.</skos:note>
  <skos:scopeNote>The Opus may be a piece of art, literature, music,
    a scientific result, or a creation within some other artistic
    or intellectual domain.</skos:scopeNote>
```

```

    <svde:closeMatch rdf:resource="http://iflastandards.info/ns/lrm/
      lrmer/E2"/>
    <svde:closeMatch rdf:resource="http://rdaregistry.info/Elements/c/
      C10001"/>
  </Class>
  <Axiom>
    <annotatedSource rdf:resource="https://svde.org/ontology/Opus"/>
    <annotatedProperty rdf:resource="http://purl.org/dc/terms/relation
      "/>
    <annotatedTarget rdf:resource="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/
      bibframe/Hub"/>
    <skos:comment>While the bf:Hub and svde:Opus are not the same,
      there is a relation among these classes in the sense they
      gather bf:Work entities by bf:hasExpression/svde:hasExpression
      respectively.</skos:comment>
  </Axiom>

```

Remark 6. The svde:Opus is a parallel class to the IFLA LRM Work and the RDA Work. The set of attributes which comprise svde:Opus parallel those attributes in the IFLA LRM Work and the RDA Work.

```

<Class rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/OpusType">
  <rdfs:label>OpusType</rdfs:label>
  <skos:definition>Individuals of the OpusType class support
    identification of Opus categories.</skos:definition>
</Class>

<Class rdf:about="https://svde.org/ontology/Work">
  <rdfs:subClassOf rdf:resource="http://id.loc.gov/ontologies/
    bibframe/Work"/>
  <rdfs:label>Work</rdfs:label>
  <skos:definition>The svde:Work is defined by a constellation of
    elements representing the specific intellectual or artistic
    form that an Opus takes each time it is realized. Individuals
    of the class svde:Work hold an Opus entity identity.</skos:
    definition>
  <svde:closeMatch rdf:resource="http://iflastandards.info/ns/lrm/
    lrmer/E3"/>
  <svde:closeMatch rdf:resource="http://rdaregistry.info/Elements/c/
    C10006"/>
</Class>

```

Remark 7. The svde:Work is a subclass of the BIBFRAME Work. The set of attributes which comprise the svde:Work parallel those attributes in the IFLA-LRM Expression and the RDA Expression.

4 Discussion

The Share-VDE ontology extends the BIBFRAME vocabulary while making references to parallel IFLA LRM and RDA classes and properties. Utilizing a set-theoretical perspective [8] to entity composition asserts parallel relationships of Share-VDE attribute sets to the attribute sets that comprise the Work classes in IFLA LRM, RDA, and BIBFRAME. Direct entity mapping of the familiar and ubiquitous conceptual approach was not utilized to achieve these concordances – rather, minimal ontological commitment is made by observing the set attributes that define an entity. Each linked data model, be it RDA, BIBFRAME or IFLA LRM, has a useful perspective, and each of these contribute to the task of bibliographic description.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper detailed the core classes and properties that comprise the Share-VDE ontology. The ontology presented herein has not been published to the web. The final steps that remain to complete the ontology are to define and add the named individuals of the `OpusType` class. Hosting the published ontology is another consideration. There is interest in publishing the Share-VDE ontology within the Library of Congress Linked Data Service. Hosting the ontology with the Library of Congress is a desirable outcome for this work given its objective to reference and extend the BIBFRAME vocabulary in support of next-generation library discovery.

References

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